

Analysis of Crimes Against Women in India and Smart Solution for Women Security

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Abstract—Women safety is an issue of utmost importance in India now because of the huge rise in the number of crimes against them. This is the solemn reality of our country that lives in constant fear. Women in India have been given equal rights as men. The proposed system analyses the crime against women and provides a solution. We use data mining techniques to analyze the increasing rates of crimes against women in India. The paper presents an IoT-based smartwatch that always connects to a phone via the internet. . The device uses IoT to communicate with the channels then send alerts to them. When the sensor readings go above the threshold values the algorithm is initiated. The GPS and GSM are used to ping the user's location directly to the police, parents, friends, and people in the near radius who have the application via the internet. ThingSpeak is used to monitor the health status of the user in every 30s. An additional feature is capturing the situation and recording 30sec audio.

Keywords: Smart Watch, IoT, ThinkSpeak, GSM, Camera, Temperature Sensor, Data Mining

I. INTRODUCTION

In this twentieth Century, Not a day goes by where you don't hear of the news of a crime against a woman in India. The list of crimes against women is increasing day by day. They are neither safe outside nor at home. There are laws but there should be a proper safe. It is possible through IoT (Internet-only measure Things). A wearable watch can be built that can track the location of the woman using the Global Position System (GPS) and send alert messages to the authorities and relatives. It works based on GPS, GSM, Body temperature sensor, pulse rate sensor.

In this project, we use sensors to detect the real-time situation of a woman. It is accomplished by the examination of physiological signals related to body reaction parameters such as galvanic skin reaction, body heartbeat, and body vibrations. These things of an individual in a dangerous situation changes and when these vitals cross the ideal values algorithm gets initiated.

The idea is to develop a smart device that is completely comfortable for women. We also collated the data entries which had criminal cases against women. These crimes can be analyzed using various techniques of data mining, which is a technique of uncovering hidden information using big data. Data Mining has become a method of investigation throughout the world now. There are several data mining techniques and they include entity extraction, decision trees, clustering, neural networks, and many more.

II. ANALYZING THE NEED OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

Violence against women is increasing day by day. Various crimes are forced upon women which include, rape, molestation, abduction, domestic violence, and more. We analyzed the crimes and cruelty faced by women in India based on previous year data. We collected all such cases reported from 2018 to 2021 and do data mining using Jovian in "colab".

We also used Jovian, which is a platform for sharing and collaborating works on colab and data science projects. After collecting the data, we prepare and clean the data, then we do exploratory analysis and cleansing. The analysis portrays a heartbreaking situation of women in our society, as more than 5 million females, over the year 2018-2021, have been a victim of assault, violence, rape, or even death, in India alone. The total entries in the training dataset is 10677. Data's such as Rape attempt, Abduction and Kidnapping, Deaths due to dowry, Assault against women with intent to outrage her modesty, Insult to the Women, Torture by Husband or his Relatives, cases of Importation of Girls are collected

Now let us analyze all the cases separately by using a bar graph.

Now we can generate a Heatmap using seaborn to represent how more cases from each state started coming up more frequently with each passing year.

Each day crime rate against women is increasing. Only 10% of the cases of woman harassment are reported above and there are still more cases yet to be reported.

As a citizen, It's our responsibility to make each woman secure. So as a measure, we proposed this system for women's security.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

Many methods are being focused on in India to prevent harassment. Some developers have come up with creative ideas such as:

- A. *191#: It provides emergency services, which will alert police. It is a free mobile application that is used to ensure the safety of women.
- B. SHE App: Society Harnessing Equipment App. This garment has an electric circuit that can help the victim to escape that gives electric shocks to the attacker.
- C. ILA SECURITY: It has alarms that will shock and disorient attackers and so safeguard the victim.
- D. VITHU App: This app will send alert messages with a location link to authorities when power button is pressed.
- E. AESHS: It is an Advanced Electronics System for Human Safety that will helps to trace the location of the victim when they attacked.
- F. Smart Belt: When the threshold of the pressure sensor raises above, the alarm will scream in the belt.

The main disadvantage of those apps and services is that the initial action has to be triggered by the victim when the victim is in perilous situations. Therefore the emphasis is to build a solution that works autonomously in situations encountered.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig 1 Main Block Diagram

Fig 2. Block Diagram Of The System

In this project, the smartphone is connected with a smartwatch using a BLE module. An interface is acting between a smartphone and a smartwatch. The Data like pulse rate, unceasing variations in the electrical attributes of the skin, caused by the variation of the human body sweating and temperature of the body, are continuously monitored by the application. In hazardous situations, the smart watch will trigger and the app will do the following tasks:-

- Alerts to the family members along with the location captured image, 30s voice recording.
- If family members find she is in danger, then they can forward these data to the police.
- Also, it will send the current location to people in the near vicinity requesting public attention.

This app helps too, send the location of the victim to family members, nearby people, and authorities through the GSM module installed in that phone.

Micro Control Unit gathers information from the smart wrist unit and GPS receiver. GSM module in the phone will then send all this information from the Micro control unit to the base station. The wrist unit gathers the data from the human

body using a body temperature sensor, pulse rate sensor, galvanic skin response, and switches. Data is sent from the wrist unit to the control unit by the RF module.

As seen in Fig 2, the smartwatch has various components:-

- A. GSM Module**
Data is sent from the control unit to the base unit this module
- B. GPS Module**
A global positioning system (GPS) used to locate the victim's latitude and longitude.
- C. Pulse Rate Sensor**
It gives a digital output of the heartbeat. Give this output to the microcontroller
- D. Temperature Sensor**
It continuously monitors the variation of the body temperature
- E. Motion Sensor**
It detects the motion of the victim and records it continuously.
- F. BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy)**
It is designed to connect devices with low power consumption that transmits small data packets as compared to Bluetooth Classic
- G. Galvanic skin responder**
It measures the unceasing variations in the electrical attributes of the skin, caused by the variation of the human body sweating.
- H. ThingSpeak**
It is an IoT platform that saves sensor data to the cloud and develops IoT applications. In the proposed system we are transmitting the data on It is used to monitor the health of a person after each 30sec.

[1] IV.ALGORITHM

When the input given by various sensors, has met the threshold value. The trigger gets initiated, and then the following actions take place:-

1. The transmitter and receiver pins of the GPS module are assigned.
2. The serial buffer is set with baud rate 9600 and then bit rate is 4800 now.
3. A loop gets initiated:
 - a) Capture images and record audio.
 - b) Data will get from the GPS module.
 - c) the longitude and latitude of the victim is obtained from GPS and convert into a Goggle URL.
 - d) Attach this URL with an image, alert message, and 30sec audio.
 - e) Send this message to the pre-selected ICE(In Case of Emergency) numbers of the relatives saved in the application.
 - f) Relatives check if it is an emergency call.
 - If yes, it will redirect to the police along with the URL.

- Else, the emergency call gets cancel

V.CONCLUSION

This idea is a precautionary step for stopping woman harassment by alerting the current status of a woman to police and relatives.

This idea can be used in various sectors for security and surveillance. It can perform real-time monitoring of the desired area and detect the accurate result of the violence.

VI . REFERENCES

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